

Deliverable D8.1 Recommended harmonised metadata model for preclinical image datasets

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Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1			Initial draft

Acronyms and Abbreviations

3Rs	Replacement, Reduction and Refinement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARRIVE	Animal Research: Reporting of In Vivo Experiments
CT	Computed Tomography
D4.1	Deliverable 4.1
EPRI	Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Imaging
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IVEP	In Vivo Experimental Parameters
MPI	Magnetic Particle Imaging
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
OI	Optical Imaging
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PAI	Photoacoustic Imaging
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PIDAR	Preclinical Image DATaset Repository
PRISM	PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SPECT	Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography
US	Ultra-Sound

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Executive Summary

The use of diverse imaging technologies in preclinical imaging research generates large volumes of heterogeneous data. Currently, the absence of standardized and structured metadata often limits the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of these datasets within the scientific community. The objective of this deliverable is to define a common metadata model for preclinical imaging datasets that meets the needs of preclinical imaging centers while supporting FAIR data management principles. To achieve this goal, the PRISM (PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata) model was developed with the involvement of international experts in preclinical imaging. The implementation of the PRISM model will improve the discoverability, interoperability, accessibility, reproducibility, and reusability of datasets across preclinical imaging infrastructures and repositories.

1. Introduction

Preclinical imaging research is generating increasingly large and heterogeneous datasets derived from multiple imaging modalities, including magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), optical imaging (OI), and other emerging technologies, which are often combined to provide complementary anatomical, functional, and molecular information. While these multimodal approaches considerably enhance the scientific value of imaging studies, they also increase the heterogeneity and complexity of the resulting datasets.

However, this rapid technological evolution has not been accompanied by a comparable level of standardization of the metadata associated with imaging datasets. Consequently, despite the growing availability of preclinical imaging data, the lack of standardized metadata limits integration, interoperability, and reuse of data within the scientific community, limiting compliance with the FAIR principles.

Several initiatives have contributed to improving metadata standardization in the imaging community. In particular, the REMBI model established important recommendations for the standardized description of biological imaging datasets, while the ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines defined essential reporting standards for animal research studies. However, preclinical imaging introduces additional challenges associated with highly specific metadata (animal strain, age, weight, and administered drug dosages), in vivo experiments, acquisitions, longitudinal studies, multimodal studies, etc., that are not comprehensively addressed by existing standards.

To overcome these limitations, this deliverable presents the development of PRISM (Preclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata), a metadata model specifically designed for preclinical imaging datasets. Building on existing community-driven standards, in particular REMBI and the ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines, PRISM aims to define a comprehensive and interoperable metadata model capable of covering the entire lifecycle of preclinical imaging studies, from study design and experimental procedures to image acquisition, correlation and analysis.

The PRISM metadata model was developed through collaboration among international experts representing different scientific disciplines and preclinical imaging modalities. To identify and prioritize the metadata elements required for a comprehensive description of preclinical imaging datasets, a structured online survey was conducted with the worldwide scientific community. The survey addressed key sections, including study design, study component, in vivo experimental parameters, image acquisition, image data, image correlation, and analyzed data.

The results of this investigation contribute to the development of a standardized model for sharing and reusing preclinical imaging data. Its implementation is expected to improve data interoperability across repositories and research infrastructures, facilitate reproducibility and data reuse, and support FAIR-compliant management and sharing of preclinical imaging data within the international scientific community.

2. Methods

2.1. Development strategy of PRISM

The PRISM (PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata) model was developed to provide a comprehensive and detailed description of preclinical imaging datasets.

The development of PRISM was based on previous initiatives and validated recommendations from the imaging community, particularly the REMBI model (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-021-01166-8>) and the ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines (<https://arriveguidelines.org/>). The model specifically focuses on the multidisciplinary nature and specific requirements of in vivo preclinical imaging studies. It builds directly on the ontology landscape analysis and recommendations established in [D4.1 \(WP4\)](#), translating ontological guidance into a structured, field-level metadata specification applicable across preclinical imaging modalities and species.

The primary objectives of the PRISM model are: (i) to develop a standardized metadata list for preclinical imaging studies; (ii) to make in vivo image datasets compliant with the FAIR principles; (iii) to improve data discoverability and reusability; and (iv) to enhance reproducibility and to align with the 3Rs Principles.

2.2. Design Principles

PRISM has been designed according to the following core principles:

FAIR compliance. Several metadata fields are linked to controlled vocabulary terms selected from the ontologies recommended in D4.1. This ensures that datasets are Findable through structured queries, Accessible via standard APIs, Interoperable across repositories, and Reusable by third parties.

Modularity. The model separates mandatory fields (required for minimal dataset description) from recommended and optional fields, enabling incremental adoption by imaging centers with varying levels of data-management maturity.

Alignment with REMBI. The PRISM categories and sub-categories mirror the REMBI top-level groupings (Study, Biosample, Specimen, Image Acquisition, Image Correlation, Analyzed Data, Analysis Overview) while adding preclinical-specific extensions described in Section 2.3.

2.3. PRISM Metadata Model Definition

The PRISM metadata model encompasses approximately 200 metadata organized into eight major sections (**Figure 1**) designed to comprehensively describe the entire lifecycle of preclinical imaging studies:

1. **Study Design:** Collects metadata describing the overall design and scientific context of the study. It includes information about the study type, background, objectives, and any associated publications.

2. **Study Component:** Records of technical and organizational details, utilizing Research Organization Registry (ROR) codes for institutions and ORCID identifiers for principal investigators. It also captures funding sources and data access conditions.
3. **In Vivo Experimental Parameters (IVEP):** Describes the experimental design and biological parameters. It includes information on study groups, sample size, randomization, blinding, outcome measures, and detailed animal characteristics.
4. **Experimental Procedures:** Documents for all interventions, including pharmacological treatments, surgical procedures, and anesthesia protocols. It specifically tracks cell lines, reagents, and specialized equipment used during the study.
5. **Image Acquisition:** Describes the technical parameters associated with image acquisition for each imaging modality. This section includes modality-specific metadata for MRI, PET, SPECT, CT, OI, US, PAI, MPI, and EPRI. Metadata includes imaging instrumentation, acquisition parameters, applied corrections, raw data availability, and quality assurance/control procedures.
6. **Image Data:** Defines the characteristics of the image dataset. It includes file formats, dimensions, spatial resolution, reconstruction algorithms, applied corrections, processing steps, and AI-based enhancements if applicable.
7. **Image Correlation:** Describes how images from different modalities or datasets are spatially and temporally correlated. It includes alignment methods, transformation matrices, fiducial markers, and relationships between related datasets.
8. **Analyzed Data:** Documents the results derived from image analysis. It includes the type of analysis performed, the data and features used, the analysis methods and software, and the format of the output files.

Figure 1. The PRISM metadata model is organized into eight major sections that collectively describe the complete lifecycle of a preclinical imaging study. These sections include: Study Design, Study Component, In Vivo Experimental Parameters (IVEP), Experimental Procedures, Image Acquisition, Image Data, Image Correlation, and Analyzed Data.

2.4. Worldwide expert survey and community consultation

To validate and refine the PRISM metadata model, after several internal rounds of discussion among the WP8 partners, an international online survey was developed and distributed using the SurveyMonkey platform [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20809198>]. The survey aimed to collect expert feedback regarding the relevance and prioritization of metadata included in PRISM.

The survey targeted professionals involved in preclinical imaging, including postdoctoral researchers, junior group leaders, associate and full professors, technical staff, and research managers. Participants represented multiple imaging modalities, including MRI, PET, SPECT, CT, OI, US, PAI, MPI, and EPRI, as well as diverse scientific disciplines such as oncology, neuroscience, cardiovascular imaging, pharmacology, image analysis and multimodal imaging research.

The survey was structured according to the eight major PRISM sections and included approximately 200 metadata elements initially selected for describing preclinical imaging datasets.

For each metadata element, participants were asked to classify the information as either:

- Mandatory metadata
- Optional metadata

Additional free-text fields were provided throughout the survey to allow participants to propose additional metadata.

The survey also collected demographic and professional information from participants, including scientific position, institutional affiliation, country, imaging expertise, research discipline, biological model systems and role within the imaging data lifecycle for statistical purposes using aggregated data.

2.5. Informed Consent

Participation in the survey was voluntary and conducted in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). All responses were analyzed in aggregate form only, and no personally identifiable information was disclosed. Participants provided informed consent electronically prior to participation in the survey.

3. Results

The PRISM metadata model was evaluated through an international online survey conducted between May and June 2026. A total of 54 experts from different preclinical imaging disciplines and institutions worldwide participated in the survey, representing 19 countries. Participants were asked to classify each metadata element as either mandatory or optional for the description of preclinical imaging datasets.

Survey participants came from a variety of geographic regions, reflecting the broad international involvement in the development of the PRISM metadata model (**Figure 2**). Survey participants represented a broad range of professional roles across the preclinical imaging community, including researchers, technical staff, associate or full professors (**Figure 3**). Most participants were affiliated with public universities or research institutes, reflecting the strong academic representation within the survey. Additional responses were provided by individuals from private companies, industry vendors, and non-profit research organizations, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives from across the preclinical imaging community (**Figure 4**).

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of survey participants.

Figure 3. Professional roles of survey participants.

Figure 4. Institutional affiliation of participants.

The survey gathered input from experts representing multiple imaging modalities and scientific disciplines, ensuring broad coverage of the preclinical imaging ecosystem (**Figure 5**). Moreover, respondents represented a broad spectrum of scientific disciplines, with multimodal and multiscale imaging among the most prevalent research areas (**Figure 6**). The survey respondents reported

experience with a variety of animal models, with mice being the most commonly investigated (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Imaging modality expertise of participants.

Figure 6. Scientific disciplines represented in the survey.

Figure 7. Animal models primarily investigated by respondents.

3.1. Consensus on PRISM metadata model

Participants evaluated metadata belonging to the eight PRISM sections:

- Study Design
- Study Component
- In Vivo Experimental Parameters (IVEP)
- Experimental Procedures
- Image Acquisition
- Image Data
- Image Correlation
- Analysed Data

Section	Total metadata	Mandatory	Optional
Study Design	12	10	2
Study Component	27	14	13
IVEP	31	25	6
Experimental Procedures	88	77	11
Image Data	18	18	0
Image Correlation	5	3	2
Analysed Data	4	4	0

Table 1. Summary of metadata results for each PRISM section.

The Image Acquisition section differs from the other PRISM sections because metadata requirements are modality specific. Therefore, acquisition metadata was organized according to the individual imaging modalities included in the model. MRI, PET, SPECT, CT, OI, US, PAI, MPI, and EPRI each contain dedicated metadata fields reflecting their technical acquisition parameters.

Imaging Modality	Total Metadata	Mandatory	Optional
MRI	17	17	0
PET	15	12	3
SPECT	18	14	4
CT	16	15	1
OI	18	12	6
US	14	13	1
PAI	17	13	4
MPI	14	10	4
EPRI	19	19	0

Table 2. Summary of metadata results for the Image Acquisition section for different imaging modalities.

Tables 3–20 present the metadata fields defined for each imaging modality, grouped into instrument specifications and image acquisition. For each metadata field, the tables report if the mandatory has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (MRI)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Magnetic field strength (in Tesla unit, e.g., 3T, 7T, ..)	Mandatory
Nuclei (e.g., 1H, 13C, 19F, 31P, etc..)	Mandatory
RF coil type (linear/quadrature, head/body/whole body)	Mandatory
RF coil size (mm)	Mandatory

Table 3. MRI instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (MRI)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Pulse Sequence Type (e.g., FSE, GRE, EPI, ..)	Mandatory
Repetition time (TR, s)	Mandatory
Echo time (TE, ms)	Mandatory
Flip Angle	Mandatory

Readout bandwidth (kHz)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Mandatory
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Mandatory

Table 4. MRI image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (PET)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Number of detectors	Optional
Type of detector (PMTs, APDs, SiPMs, CZT, ..)	Optional
Isotope (e.g., ^{11}C , ^{18}F , ..)	Mandatory

Table 5. PET instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (PET)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Static or dynamic acquisition	Mandatory
Acquisition mode (frame-mode, list-mode, ..)	Mandatory
Total injected activity (MBq)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Mandatory
Correction (details on corrections : e.g., for PET: decay correction, random correction, dead time correction, attenuation correction; for CT: beam hardening correction, ring artifact correction)	Mandatory
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Optional

Table 6. PET image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (SPECT)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory

Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Number of detector heads	Optional
Type of collimator used (single, multi-pinhole, etc..)	Mandatory
Energy window used (keV)	Mandatory
Isotope (e.g., 99mTc, 68Ga, 123I, ...)	Mandatory
Pinhole size (mm)	Optional

Table 7. SPECT instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (SPECT)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Number of projections per image	Optional
Number of detected counts	Optional
Acquisition mode (frame-mode, list-mode, ..)	Mandatory
Total injected activity (MBq)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory

Scan time (minutes)	Mandatory
Correction (details on corrections : e.g., for PET: decay correction, random correction, dead time correction, attenuation correction; for CT: beam hardening correction, ring artifact correction)	Mandatory
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Mandatory

Table 8. SPECT image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (CT)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Number of sources	Mandatory
Beam energy (kVp)	Mandatory
Current (mA)	Mandatory

Table 9. CT instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (CT)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Number of projections	Mandatory
Step size (degree)	Mandatory
Acquisition mode (e.g., axial, helical, multi-slice, cone-beam, ..)	Mandatory
Dose (mGy)	Mandatory
Exposure time (ms)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Mandatory
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Optional

Table 10. CT image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (OI)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory

Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Bioluminescent or Fluorescent Imaging	Mandatory
Sensor type (CMODS, CCD, ..)	Optional
Type of illumination (Epi, Trans-illumination, ..)	Mandatory
Illumination power or irradiance (mW/cm ²)	Optional
Type of fluorophore (fluorescent dye, ..)	Mandatory

Table 11. OI instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (OI)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Excitation wavelengths (nm)	Mandatory
Emission or detection wavelengths (nm)	Mandatory
Binning	Optional
F-stop (aperture)	Optional

Exposure time (s)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Optional
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Optional

Table 12. OI image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (US)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Transducer Operating Frequency (MHz)	Mandatory
Type of transducer (e.g. linear, convex, phased array, ..)	Mandatory

Table 13. US instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (US)	Requirement
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Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Acquisition mode (e.g., B-mode, Color doppler, etc)	Mandatory
Frame rate (fps)	Mandatory
Number of frames	Mandatory
Slice thickness	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Optional
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Mandatory

Table 14. US image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (PAI)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory

Laser type (e.g., Nd:YAG, pulsed laser diode, light emitting diode, ..)	Optional
Scanning System (Fixed for 2D or rotational/translational for 3D)	Mandatory
Detector geometry (linear array, cylindrical, and hemispherical)	Mandatory
Detector broadband frequency (MHz)	Optional

Table 15. PAI instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (PAI)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Laser wavelength range (nm)	Mandatory
Laser pulse energy (mJ)	Mandatory
Laser pulse width (ns)	Mandatory
Laser pulse repetition rate (Hz)	Mandatory
Detector broadband frequency (MHz)	Mandatory
Axial resolution (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Optional
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory

QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Optional
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Table 16. PAI image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (MPI)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Field-free region (e.g., FFP or FFL)	Optional
Drive Field Frequency (kHz)	Mandatory

Table 17. MPI instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (MPI)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Type of projections (2D or 3D)	Mandatory
Drive Field Amplitude (mT)	Mandatory
Selection field gradient (T/m)	Mandatory

Tracer type (e.g., SPIO, USPIO, ..)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Optional
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Optional
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Optional

Table 18. MPI image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Instrument specifications (EPRI)	Requirement
Instrument vendor (vendor name)	Mandatory
Instrument type (commercial name of the imaging instrumentation used, e.g., Pharmascan 70/16 or Mediso nanoScan PET/CT or MILabs U-SPECT or IVIS Spectrum or VEVO F2 or Magnetic Insight MOMENTUM or O2M Technologies JIVA-25 EPRI System)	Mandatory
Software name and version	Mandatory
Static magnetic field (MHz)	Mandatory
Magnetic modulation field (mT)	Mandatory
Magnetic field sweep width (mT)	Mandatory
Magnetic field gradient (mT/cm)	Mandatory

Resonator type (e.g., loop-gap, Alderman-Grant, surface coils, ..)	Mandatory
Resonator size (mm)	Mandatory

Table 19. EPRI instrument specifications metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

Image acquisition (EPRI)	Requirement
Field of View (FOV, cm)	Mandatory
Acquisition mode (CW or pulsed)	Mandatory
Number of projections	Mandatory
Field sweep time per projection (ms)	Mandatory
Digital bandpass filter (kHz)	Mandatory
Type of paramagnetic probe (e.g., trityl, nitroxyl, ..)	Mandatory
Voxel size (μm)	Mandatory
Scan time (minutes)	Mandatory
Raw data (are raw data available for custom reconstruction? yes/no)	Mandatory
QA/QC (are available info on Quality Assurance/Quality Check? yes/no)	Mandatory

Table 20. EPRI image acquisition metadata included in the PRISM metadata model. For each metadata field, the tables report if the metadata has been voted as mandatory or optional.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the development of the PRISM metadata model and of the results obtained from a well-accepted worldwide consultation, for establishing a standardized metadata model for preclinical image datasets. PRISM extends the REMBI model with preclinical-specific categories covering experimental context, in vivo experimental procedures and in vivo modality-specific acquisition parameters, while remaining fully aligned with the FAIR data principles and the ontologies recommended in [D4.1](#).

PRISM has been implemented in the PIDAR platform (<https://pidar.hpc4ai.unito.it/Datasets/Index>) to demonstrate the utility of this metadata model. The PRISM model will continue to evolve in response to community feedback and for including new imaging modalities that will be developed in the near future.